

Milligram Level Determination of Cobalt, Iridium and Rhodium : *m*-(Mercaptoacetamido)phenol as a Gravimetric Reagent

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m-(Mercaptoacetamido)phenol is proposed as a gravimetric reagent for the milligram level determination of cobalt, iridium and rhodium. The metal ions are precipitated as CoR_2 , IrR_3 , and RhR_2 at pH 6.5 to 8.5, 2.5 to 4 and 2.5 to 4, respectively as purple-red, light orange and deep orange products, respectively; R being a deprotonated molecule of the reagent. The platinum metals can be determined in the presence of cobalt and all these metals in the presence of most related metals. The reagent possesses the desirable qualities of a gravimetric reagent.

IN the earlier publications we introduced *m*-(mercaptoacetamido)phenol (abbreviated as *m*-MAP, formula I) as a hydrophilic reagent for the qualitative¹⁻³ and quantitative^{4,5} inorganic analysis. In the present paper we report the use of this reagent as a gravimetric reagent for semimicro estimation of cobalt, iridium, and rhodium. These and other platinum metals⁵ can be estimated in the presence of cobalt and all the determinants in the presence of most sulphide forming cations.

The precipitation reactions of *m*-MAP with common metal ions are already reported³.

Experimental

Reagents

Preparation of the Reagent : Condense equimolecular amounts of thioglycolic acid and *m*-aminophenol at 110° for 3 hrs under a perpetual layer of 1:1 benzene and toluene (to avoid aerial oxidation of the reaction mixture) using a moderately long air condenser.

Scrub the crude product thrice with 1*N* hydrochloric acid, 50 ml for each 10 g of the product, to remove the unreacted reactants. Recrystallise at room temperature from ethanol to obtain colorless crystals (m.p. 161°, yield 50%).

For use as a reagent, dissolve 0.5 g of *m*-MAP in 20 ml of ethanol and dilute the solution to 100 ml with HCl (pH2). Prepare fresh solution every day.

Cobalt(II), iridium(III) and rhodium(III) were used as chlorides (0.1% solution). The metal ions, of which the effect upon the estimation of the determinants was seen, were taken as the solutions (1.0%) of the water

soluble salts. Other chemicals were used as solutions of the Reagent Grade supply. A single-pan semimicro balance reading accurately to 0.01 mg was used throughout the investigation.

Procedure

Diluted an aliquot of the solution, containing about 5 mg of the determinant, to 50 ml with distilled water. Adjusted the pH of the solution, 6.5 for cobalt and 2.5 for iridium or rhodium. Added at least 5 mole of *m*-MAP for each mole of the metal ion and readjusted the pH. Added 100 mg of ammonium sulphate as a coagulant for cobalt. Digested the precipitates on a steam bath for 30 to 45 mins to coagulate. The precipitate of cobalt is purple red, whereas the precipitates due to platinum metals are orange. Filtered the precipitate using a G 3 sintered crucible.

Cleaned the beaker and the stirring rod as follows : Rinsed this apparatus with an aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide at pH 11 (5 ml) to dissolve the precipitate (each precipitate dissolves due to the phenolic group in the molecule). Now progressively added 5 ml solution of ammonium chloride until the alkali was neutralised and the precipitate reappeared. Transferred it to the crucible and washed the whole lot thrice with 10-ml portions of hot distilled water. Dried the precipitates at 100° and weighed.

Results and Discussion

Typical results are shown in Table I. The composition of the precipitates, viz., 1:2 for cobalt (II) and rhodium (II) and 1:3 for iridium (III), is also supported by elemental analysis given in Table 2.

The gravimetric results with these metal ions are obtained with the same accuracy in the presence of most related foreign metal ions. The amounts of the latter tolerated are shown in Table 3 and any necessary modification of the estimation procedure is indicated in the foot notes to the same Table. In such determinations, the precipitate of the determinant should always be filtered from boiling hot media.

S. N. KAKKAR & N. S. POONIA : MILLIGRAM LEVEL DETERMINATION OF COBALT,

TABLE 1.—HOWING THE REPRESENTATIVE RESULTS AND PRECISION OF GRAVIMETRIC ESTIMATIONS OF COBALT, IRIIDIUM AND RHODIUM WITH *m*-MAP.

Cation (amount in mg)	Amount of the complex isolated, mg.	Amount of the cation ^a calc., mg.	Percent error	Standard deviation for six est imations.
Cobalt (5.000 mg)	35.60	4.963	-0.74	0.11
	35.90	5.005	0.10	
	36.10	5.032	0.64	
Iridium (5.000 mg)	19.05	4.976	-0.48	0.09
	19.15	5.002	0.04	
	19.27	5.033	0.66	
Rhodium (5.000 mg)	22.54	4.972	-0.56	0.10
	22.58	4.981	-0.38	
	22.76	5.021	0.42	

a Conversion factors for cobalt, iridium and rhodium are 0.1394, 0.2612 and 0.2200 respectively.

TABLE 2—SHOWING THE ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS (C,H,N) FOR THE *m*-MAP PRODUCTS OF COBALT, IRIIDIUM AND RHODIUM.

Compound	Found			Calculated		
	C	H	N	C	H	N
Co(C ₈ NO ₂ SH ₈) ₂	45.33	3.91	6.59	45.39	3.76	6.62
Ir(C ₈ NO ₂ SH ₈) ₃	39.81	3.49	5.48	38.97	3.25	5.70
Rh(C ₈ NO ₂ SH ₈) ₂	41.76	3.60	5.85	41.11	3.43	5.99

TABLE 3—SHOWING THE AMOUNTS OF THE FOREIGN IONS TOLERATED DURING THE GRAVIMETRIC ESTIMATIONS OF COBALT, IRIIDIUM AND RHODIUM

Foreign Ion Added	The amount of the foreign ion added, mg, while estimating :	
	Cobalt(5 mg)	Iridium or Rhodium(5 mg).
Cu(I,II), Ag	50 ^a	50 ^b
Au(III)	50 ^a	50 ^c
Ni(II)	20 ^d	50
Zn	5 ^e , 15 ^f	50
Fe(III)	50 ^e	50
Fe(II)	50 ^g	50
As(V,III)	10 ^{i,h}	10
Sb(VI,II)	5 ^e , 20 ⁱ	50 ^k
Sn(IV, II)	20 ^{i,h} , 20 ⁱ	50 ^k
Hg(II)	20 ^{i,h}	—
Pb(II)	—	50 ^e
Bi	5 ⁱ	50 ^e
Cd	20 ⁱ	—
Pt(IV), Pd,Ru(III)	20 ^a	50 ^e

General notes. 50 mg of the following ions were tolerated in each estimation with the standard procedure: Al(III), Cr(III), Mn(II), Zr(IV), Th(IV), Ti(I,III), uranyl, vanadyl, ammonium, alkali and alkaline earth metal ions and lanthanum. *Caution*: Use enough *m*-MAP so that the foreign ion is masked as well.

Upper limit of tolerance is studied for cases the amount is shown in italics.

In case no superscript is given, the standard procedure is followed.

Dash means estimation is not possible.

- Eliminate the foreign ion with *m*-MAP at pH 2.5-3 and estimate cobalt in the filtrate. *Caution*; Adjust pH before adding *m*-MAP.
- Add solid KI to the solution until the iodide of the foreign ion has redissolved and then follow the standard procedure. To avoid the reprecipitation of the iodide

of the foreign ion during washing, give first three washings to the precipitate with 20 percent aqueous KI and finally with hot distilled water until free of iodide.

- Adjust the pH of the solution at 6-7, add 20 ml of EDTA (sodium salt) per mole of the foreign ion and heat for an hour. Filter metallic gold and estimate the determinant in the filtrate as usual.
- Remove nickel using dimethylglyoxime, destroy the excess of this reagent with HClO₄-H₂SO₄ in the filtrate and estimate cobalt as usual.
- Use 0.5% tartrate in the precipitation media.
- Add *m*-MAP sufficient to react with all the cations and then ethanol to clear the solution from the precipitate so produced. Adjust the pH of the solution at 6-7 and expell alcohol from the solution on steam bath (whilst partially covering the beaker) until cobalt is reprecipitated and the medium colour is not reddish. *Caution*. Do not expell alcohol beyond this point. From the hot media filter the precipitate by decantation using a G4 sintered crucible.
- Oxidise ferrous in the test solution by heating with minimum amount of concentrated nitric acid and then follow as in the case of the ferric estimation.
- Precipitate out all the cations with *m*-MAP at pH 6-7. Progressively add aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (pH 11) to obtain a blood red solution free of any suspension. Now slowly add 1M solution of ammonium chloride until the pH is lowered to 8.5 (not below). Cobalt is reprecipitated. Now process as usual. Give first washing with aqueous solution of sodium acetate (pH 8) and then with water.
- Adjust the pH of the solution at 2.5-3 and add a solution of the reagent in cold to precipitate out the foreign ion. Shake the reaction mixture in ice cold water for five minutes and filter the residue. Now follow instruction 'f'.
- Eliminate most of the foreign ion as above and then follow instruction 'h'.
- Follow instruction 'e' and keep the pH of the precipitation medium strictly at 2.5.

Thionalide and α -nitroso- β -naphthol are the most widely used gravimetric reagents for cobalt and the platinum metals^{6,7}, the former for cobalt essentially for the reason it can estimate this metal in the presence of nickel. Both reagents are, however, practically water-insoluble and invariably produce contaminated metal products. Both are general precipitants for the sulphide-forming metal ions and platinum metals. α -nitroso- β -naphthol even colours the precipitation media dark brown. *m*-MAP compares favourably with these reagents in view of these and the following points.

It is an easily prepared colorless crystalline compound which does not colour the precipitation media. It can be freely used in the aqueous media; 1 g can be easily accommodated in 100 ml boiling water. Metal complexes of constant composition are isolated from aqueous media which are in a weighable form.

The reagent works in the acid medium so that the precipitates are granular and easily filterable. Inorganic electrolytes, if present, do not affect the composition of the precipitates but rather improve their granulation. For cobalt, the inorganic anions which precipitate cobalt in feeble acid medium should be absent, although equivalent amounts of such anion, even phosphate, can be tolerated provided the *m*-MAP solution is mixed with cobalt at pH 2 and then the pH is raised to 6.5. The slow rise of pH favours the precipitation of the metal ion with *m*-MAP as against that of the inorganic salt.

m-MAP can be made to behave more selectively than any of the two reagents quoted above not only by the use of masking agents and the adjustment of the pH of the media of precipitation but also by raising the temperature of the same. It is so because hydroxyl (phenolic) group in the reagent enhances its hydrophilicity and so influences the lattice energy of the metal complexes that the same do not precipitate out of media at high temperature.

The platinum and coinage metal ions can be estimated in the presence of cobalt, and the latter can be then estimated from the filtrate. Platinum metals are estimated in the presence of most others.

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